

Uzbek Khan Atlas and Snipe

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Abstract: Khan-atlas is a traditional Uzbek fabric made of dense silk fabric. The fabric has interesting complex weaves, and its dyeing is carried out with natural multi-colored dyes. The classic traditional Uzbek fabric khan-atlas is closely connected with the Uzbek culture and history, reflecting the national specifics of the Uzbek people. This research paper is devoted to the study of the history of the Uzbek fabric Khan Atlas. Particular attention is paid to such aspects as: description of the fabric produced according to the traditional technology of the silkworm abra-ikat; the uniqueness of the technique and design of the Uzbek striped fabric — "atlas"; Separation of Avra fabrics by type of raw material; the use of these fabrics in everyday life. The paper tries to show that the Uzbek atlas and adras have become part of the world cultural heritage.

Keywords: Abra-ikat; Bekasam; Khan-atlas; The Uzbek culture; Uzbekistan

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1. Introduction

Thousands of years have passed since the time of the ancient caravanners. The goods carried by camels were amazing in variety and quality. Among them was the royal, or, as it is called in Uzbekistan, khan atlas (royal silk), which is still in demand in the East and in the world and is a special attraction of the country. Khan-atlas is the pearl of Uzbekistan. This exquisite textile captures the spirit and customs of the Uzbek people. Khan silk represents friendliness, optimism, and boundless vitality with its distinctive vibrant color palette and smooth texture. Atlas, translated from Arabic, literally means "smooth", and therefore the fabric is named after one of its main features. Almost every nation on our planet boasts its own attributes. These have always included the national attire whose style is dependent on the geographical location of the country, the economic component, and other factors. Deeply rooted in antiquity, the Uzbek fabrics have preserved the richness of the cultural heritage of the eastern peoples and traces of the historical past. One of the oldest sorts of handicraft is the production of fabric. The art of fabric making, on the basis of long-standing traditions, is being developed and improved in Uzbekistan. Its quality and distinctive feature is reflected in reports, articles and books (Beschastnov, 2010; Menges, 2013; Pulatova, 2015; Sayidafzal 2017; Siddikov, 2017) .

2. Description of the fabric produced by the traditional technology of silkworm abr-ikat

The satin is distinguished by a special unique type of weave, not only with a smooth, but also with a shiny surface, since a more valuable fiber is located on the upper basis. Among these fabrics, which are widely produced in Central Asia,

the textile fabric produced according to the traditional technology of the silkworm "abr", meaning "cloud", is of particular interest.

Regarding production methods, there are two main categories of abr fabrics: silk fabrics, in which the weft is made of natural silk, and fabrics like adras, in which the weft is made of cotton threads and the wrap is made of natural silk. Abra-ikat is the name under which fabrics are known in the West. Later, the word "abr" began to be used in the designing of the style of thread dyeing in traditional fabrics. Thus, fabrics began to be called abr, and their creators-weavers were called abrbands. The classic traditional Uzbek abr fabric is made from the cocoons of the Uzbek silkworm. It is no coincidence that the word "ikat" comes from the Indonesian verb "mengikat", which means "to bind". Therefore, the "abrbandi" method consists in the reservation of individual sections of the base by ligation, followed by staining them in certain colors. Such a technique, according to the pattern and coloring, created an interesting artistic effect, while the ornament at the same time acquired vague contours and, with slightly outlined indefinite forms, turned into a play of colored spots. Thus, when the fabric is woven, peculiar, unique patterns appear on it, consisting of iridescent colored stains (khan-atlas) or alternating colored stripes (snipes). (Fig.1) Everything is done entirely by hand, so it can take a whole week of painstaking work to create one standard cut. Among the wonderful traditions that are rich in the art of the peoples of Central Asia, a special place is occupied by the artistic design of textile materials. For example, unlike ordinary fabrics, a pattern on abr fabrics is first created on the basis, and then woven and finished (Menges, 2013: 35–40). Each school of silk weaving in Central Asia was famous for its ornamental art. The composition of the abr drawing was distinguished by a variety of motifs. They combined geometric, floral and object motifs, as well as stylized images of jewelry. The motif of a ram's horn (Tagalyak), which is widespread in the ornamentation of the cattle-breeding tribes of Central Asia, in all likelihood, influenced the elements of a plant pattern in the art of some settled agricultural peoples. As a result, along with a new name, one of the types of shoot acquired the corresponding forms of stylization, in some cases really resembling a schematic ram's horn (Pulatova, 2015: 103).

Figure 1: Abr fabrics.

3. The uniqueness of the technique and design of the Uzbek striped fabric - "atlas"

In the 19th century, striped fabrics created by weaving continued to be widely distributed among the population of Central Asia. In the second half of this century, weaving in Uzbekistan became the most developed branch of the craft (Beschastnov, 2010: 335). The art of warping during this period reached its highest perfection, allowing fabrics with interesting striped patterns to be formed in a relatively simple way. Of course, this is a significant merit of the hereditary masters of this ancient craft. However, in the middle of the 20th century, they began to be persecuted by the authorities. (Sayidafzal, 2020: 56). After the cessation of the work of handicraft workshops, all the features of the traditional fabrics of the peoples of Central Asia began to be forgotten. Despite this, many of them tried to preserve the traditions of this beautiful art form and pass them on to the younger generation. This situation did not last long, and by the 1970s,

Uzbekistan again had the opportunity to engage in hand weaving. In the old centers, especially in some cities of the Ferghana Valley, the production of snipes and other striped semi-silk fabrics is being restored, which retain local originality in color and rhythm in the composition.

In the early 1990s, due to the revival of traditional customs and festivities, increased attention to the national character of clothing, handmade fabrics again became in demand among the population. At that time, many experts from various international organizations, interested in the development of the local market, visited Central Asia. Among them there were many high-class specialists who sincerely want to help the artisans of Uzbekistan to reach the international level. In particular, the best friend of all the weavers in Margilan was an expert from England, Phelippa Watkins, arrived within the framework of the grant program of the British Council. Thanks to her fine work on changing the design of fabrics and the efforts of local specialists, the center for the production of handmade fabrics was revived center production Margilan Yedgorlik factory. Traditional artistic weaving has been one of the most prominent forms of Uzbekistan's modern national art since the early 21st century. Margilan is currently home to the largest Khan Atlas producing facility. Since ancient times, the production of atlases and adras has been centered in Margilan. For their khan-atlases with fluttering rainbow designs and printed silk garments, the city of silk rose to global fame. Margilan silk was transported by traders via the Great Silk Road in the Middle Ages to Baghdad, Kashgar, Khorasan, Egypt, and Greece. Margilan has proudly upheld its title as the East's silk capital for many years. Long specializing in the production of silk materials, its people have achieved recognition for it is enough to visit this city once to fall in love with the most beautiful fabric. Khan-atlas can be purchased not only in Margilan, but also in other cities of Uzbekistan: Kokand, Bukhara, Samarkand, and Khiva. The production of these beautiful fabrics, as in the past, is carried out by entire dynasties that have deep roots in the Uzbek land. Even today they strive to enrich traditional drawings with completely new themes, in accordance with modern requirements. The later striped fabric - bekasam - continues to occupy one of the leading places in the modern national assortment of textile products in Uzbekistan. They form certain parts of production. Bekasam used to be used to sew outfits for the bride. This tradition continues to this day.

4. Separation of Avra fabrics by type of raw material and the use of these fabrics in everyday life

Making a khan-atlas by hand is a laborious operation that takes up to forty steps. Pomegranate peels, onion peels, madder, and extracts from roots, fruits, and plants are only a few examples of the natural materials utilized as colors. A special dyeing technique creates a unique pattern, such a pattern is called abr - a cloud. The classic traditional Uzbek fabric khan-atlas is made from the cocoons of the Uzbek silkworm. Khan-atlas comes in several types of 100% silk, 50% x 50% silk with cotton and with the addition of gold or silver luxur. Bright, colorful, with an unforgettable and unique corner ornament, the colors are often called ikat; the Uzbek fabric khan-atlas often attracts the attention of world-famous fashion designers and fashion designers. Khan-atlas is a colorful and bright fabric with unique bright and colorful ornaments. In ancient times, not everyone could afford clothes made from khan-atlas. The fabric was considered very expensive and difficult to obtain. Every oriental girl with great pride put on dresses made of khan-atlas. Khan-atlas today adorns not only women from Uzbekistan, but also from all over the world. You can meet the Uzbek fabric khan-atlas in the collections of world-famous fashion designers. Like many centuries ago, today the khan-atlas fabric is a brand of Uzbekistan. A fabric with a rainbow unique ornament continues to reign among other types of fabrics and pleases its owners with unusual brightness, beauty and tenderness. This fabric is unique and inimitable; it is always different. The later striped fabric - bekasam - continues to occupy one of the leading places in the modern national assortment of textile products in Uzbekistan. They form certain parts of production. Bekasam used to be used to sew outfits for the bride. This tradition continues to this day. Khan-atlas, like snipes, is formed by color stripes that do not have clear boundaries. If the abrband method is used in the technological process to obtain an abr pattern on a fabric, then a mannered warp pattern can be used to obtain striped patterns. As a result of choosing the optimal one from various technological processes, a new fabric "abrov snipe" was obtained, which is protected by a patent of the

Republic of Uzbekistan. The author, Siddikov, is a professor at the Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry and a doctor of technical sciences (Siddikov, 2017: 161-169). Since ancient times, the value of Uzbek silk has been so high that it was equal to the bride's jewelry, which should be as much as possible at the wedding. Therefore, images of jewelry were applied to the canvas as a pattern. One of the historians of the Middle Ages wrote: "In terms of its value, a section of the Margelan khan atlas is in no way inferior to the value of all the lands of Bukhara." Margilan was a significant hub for trade and cross-cultural interaction because of its location along the Great Silk Road caravan routes. Since the third century AD, this city's artists have been creating silk fabrics that merchants have shipped to numerous locations in Europe and Asia.

Legends from ancient times claim that one of the monarchs of Margilan once fell in love with the daughter of a poor weaver and decided to make her his fifth bride. This is claimed to be true of royal silk. The girl's father knelt at the khan's feet and begged him to let his baby daughter go. The ruler agreed, but only on the condition that by dawn, the weaver would produce something so exquisite that it will eclipse the girl's beauty. The dejected old guy went to the canal's banks and sat there for a while introspectively, not noting how his tears were mingled with the rain. Then, out of nowhere, the rain stopped and clouds emerged in the sky, which he could see in the water's reflection. Oh, god, thank you for the thought! he exclaimed as the clouds changed into every hue of the rainbow. He went to his workshop and worked all night. In the morning, he unfolded an extraordinary fabric in front of the khan that was airy like a cloud and light as air and shimmered with every hue of the rainbow. The emperor was astounded by the exquisiteness of the fabric, so he decided to forget about his wife and let her leave. The fabric of incredible beauty was called khan silk - khan-atlas. In the old days, the center of silk weaving was Bukhara. But the silkworms of Margilan began to weave colorful fabrics so skillfully that to this day the khan - atlas from Margilan is considered one of the best.

5. Uzbek atlas and adras in the world cultural heritage list

Register of Excellence for the Preservation of the Intangible Cultural Heritage lists the historical techniques used to produce satin and adras, the traditional Uzbek silk fabrics.

At its 12th conference, the Intergovernmental Committee for the Preservation of the Intangible Cultural Heritage, held in Jeju, the South Republic of Korea, the decision was taken of putting Uzbek atlas and adras in the world cultural heritage list.

The Ferghana Valley's Uzbek Margilan, which has a long history of producing atlas and adras, natural fabrics with a distinctive design, is mentioned in the UNESCO judgment. A Center for the Development of Traditional Culture was established in 2007 to help revive and protect the vanishing traditions. The center is engaged in the preservation, development and popularization of the production of atlas and adras (Torebaev, 2017: 222). Its employees hold classes, exhibitions and craft fairs for those wishing to get acquainted with the ancient craft, as well as publishing guides dedicated to the preservation of traditional technology. Thus, the fabric is rather popular in Central Asia. From it various forms of costume for girls and women are traditionally sewn; and it has regained its former glory. Khan-atlas again adorns not only local women, but also many women from near and far abroad. Recently, on the world's catwalks, you can often see beauties from all over the world, and not only oriental ones, in clothes made from this most beautiful and delicate fabric. So, the traditional fabrics of the peoples of Central Asia are not only of historical and everyday significance, but also of great artistic value. Today, like many centuries ago, khan-atlas, striking with its riot of colors, its originality and splendor, is one of the most recognizable brands of Uzbekistan. Even modern foreign fashion designers have paid special attention to it. Interestingly, this amazing and truly feminine fabric is used in their collections by world-famous designers: Oscar de la Renta, Gucci, John Galliano, Monsoon, Alex Mabille. We see these prints in the collections of Zaitsev, Yudashkin and Van Noten. It should be recalled that the first designer on the Russian podium, who showed the public products from khan-atlas, is Elena Suprun. Well-known Kazakh couturier Aidarkhan Kaliev, chief designer of the Asyl-Design fashion house, creator of the Aspara clothing brand. A collection of clothes

with artistic and coloristic design, repeating the pattern of the khan-atlas of many fashion designers from different countries, was noticed on the foreign podium. When creating their outfits, they use these textiles and American model houses: Mango, Zara, Dolce & Cabana, etc(Torebaev, 2017: 118).

6. Conclusion

Bright colors and bold patterns have not become outdated for many decades, and on the contrary, they are becoming popular both in the East and in the West. Ethnic zest on the one hand, the fabric is very practical to use and open to experiments. The manufacture of Uzbek textiles from silk using a long-forgotten technique was invented back in the fabric was distributed. It is not surprising that Central Asia became the region where such a vibrant and high-quality fabric was distributed. The designs of the adras reflect the idea of the diversity of peoples and cultures whose caravans passed through Bukhara, Margilan, Samarkand, Khujand, and other historic places that continue to manufacture adras today. People's religious views and moral and ethical values were reflected in traditional Uzbek clothing. The study of ethnic history, rites, and customs must consider the Uzbek traditional fabric because it is one of the most enduring phenomena of traditional culture. It is impossible to imagine our entire culture without the said material, which has served as a symbol of luxury for many centuries.

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